

IN-SILICO IDENTIFICATION AND EXPLORATION OF ACTIVE INGREDIENTS AGAINST STROKE FROM RIPENED FRUIT OF PALMYRA PALM

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ABSTRACT: Stroke is one of the cerebrovascular illnesses and the second leading cause of death and disability worldwide. Treatment begins with taking drugs that break up clots and prevent new ones from forming. Both steroidal saponins and monounsaturated fatty acids are extremely effective against stroke. Molecular docking is the foundation for stroke treatment in this research perspective. From the perspective of protein-ligand interaction research, the treatment option for stroke was investigated using Auto Dock for molecular docking. According to the study's findings, Flabelliferin-A and Palmitoleic acid exhibit superior binding interactions and have extremely high potencies for stroke. We hope to develop new medications to treat challenging medical conditions like stroke using the chemicals generated by our screening process.

keywords: Cerebrovascular stroke, treatment, molecular docking, protein ligand interaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

1. STROKE

A stroke, also known as a brain attack, happens when a brain blood vessel bursts or when something stops the flow of blood to a certain area of the brain. Either way, certain brain regions suffer harm or even die. A stroke can result in permanent impairment, death, or irreversible brain damage.^[1]

A transient ischemic attack, also known as a "mini-stroke," can occur at any time. Because the blood supply to the brain is cut off for a brief period of time—typically no longer than five minutes—it differs from the major type of stroke. TIAs are occasionally referred to as "warning strokes." It is crucial to understand that, because blood clots frequently cause TIAs, it is impossible to determine at the outset whether symptoms are due to a TIA or a more serious kind of stroke, such as ischemic strokes. Within a year after having a TIA, over one-third of those who do not receive treatment go on to have a major stroke. Within three months of having a TIA, 10% to 15% of people will experience a major stroke. Recognizing and treating TIAs can lower the risk of a major stroke. If you have a TIA, your health care team can find the cause and take steps to prevent a major stroke.^{[2],[3]}

Ischemic stroke: The majority of strokes is ischemic strokes. Blood clots or other debris obstruct the blood vessels leading to the brain can cause an ischemic stroke. By accumulating in the blood vessels, fatty deposits known as plaque can also result in blockages.^[4]

Hemorrhagic stroke: When a cerebral artery bursts or leaks blood, it can cause a hemorrhagic stroke. The blood leak damages brain cells by applying excessive pressure to them. Aneurysms balloon-like bulges in an artery that have the potential to stretch and burst and high blood pressure are two factors that can result in a hemorrhagic stroke.^[5]

1.1. What happens in the brain during a stroke?

The brain is the source of our thoughts, feelings, language, and motor control. It also stores memories. Breathing and digestion are just two of the numerous bodily processes that the brain regulates. Air is necessary for the brain to function properly. Your arteries carry blood enriched with oxygen to every area of your brain. Brain cells begin to die within minutes of anything obstructing the blood supply because they are deprived of oxygen. This causes a stroke. In the below figure 1 shows the pathophysiology of stroke.

1.2. Symptoms Take close note of when the symptoms started if you think you or someone you know is having a stroke. Certain treatments work best when started shortly after the onset of a stroke. Among the symptoms and indicators of a stroke are:

- Trouble speaking and understanding what others are saying
- Paralysis or numbness of the face, arm or leg
- Problems seeing in one or both eyes
- Headache
- Trouble walking^[6]

1.3. Risk factors: Many factors can increase the risk of stroke. Potentially treatable stroke risk factors include:

1.3.1. Lifestyle risk factors like being overweight or obese, Physical inactivity, Heavy or binge drinking and Use of illegal drugs such as cocaine and methamphetamine

1.3.2. Medical risk factors include High blood pressure, Cigarette smoking or second-hand smoke exposure, High cholesterol, Diabetes, Obstructive sleep apnea, cardiovascular disease, including heart failure, heart defects, heart infection or irregular heart rhythm, such as atrial fibrillation, Personal or family history of stroke, heart attack or transient ischemic attack and COVID-19 infection.

1.3.3. Age: People age 55 or older have a higher risk of stroke than do younger people.

1.3.4. Race or ethnicity: African Americans and Hispanics have a higher risk of stroke than do people of other races or ethnicities.

1.3.5. Sex: Men have a higher risk of stroke than do women. Women are usually older when they have strokes, and they're more likely to die of strokes than are men.

1.3.6. Hormones: Use of birth control pills or hormone therapies that include oestrogen increases risk.^{[7],[8]}

1.4. Complications of stroke: Depending on which part of the brain is affected and for how long, a stroke can result in either permanent or temporary disabilities. Complications may include:

- Paralysis or loss of muscle movement
- Difficulty talking or swallowing
- Memory loss or thinking difficulties and Emotional problems
- Changes in behaviour and self-care ability

1.5. How to prevent?

There are many heart disease and stroke prevention tactics that are similar. Following a transient ischemic attack (TIA) or stroke, these precautions may help avoid another stroke. You're in-hospital and post-discharge follow-up care may also be important. Healthy lifestyle suggestions generally consist of Controlling hypertension and Managing diabetes

- Lowering the amount of cholesterol and saturated fat in your diet.
- Quitting tobacco use and Drinking alcohol
- Maintaining a healthy weight and exercising regularly
- Eating a diet rich in fruits and vegetables
- Treating obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) and avoiding illegal drugs ^{[9],[10]}

1.5.1. Anti-platelet drugs: Blood cells called platelets are what cause clots. Antiplatelet medications reduce the stickiness and clotting potential of these cells. Aspirin and clopidogrel (Plavix), when taken together, are the most often used anti-platelet medications. They lower the risk of having another stroke over time.^[11]

1.5.2. Anticoagulants: These medicines lessen the clotting of blood. Because of its quick onset of action, heparin can be used briefly. It may use Jantoven, a slower-acting warfarin, for an extended period of time. For those who are at a higher risk of stroke, there are a number of more recent blood-thinning drugs called anticoagulants. Apixaban (Eliquis), rivaroxaban (Xarelto), dabigatran (Pradaxa), and edoxaban (Savaysa) are some of these drugs.^[12]

1.6. PLANT BASED COPE FOR STROKE

1.6.1. Steroidal saponins

Many plants form secondary metabolites called saponins; these include the Arecaceae, Araliaceae, Leguminosae, Polygalaceae, Campanulaceae, Dioscoreaceae, Liliaceae, and Scrophulariaceae families. Amphipathic glycosides that consist of a sugar chain and either a triterpene or steroid aglycone group. The antiplatelet and anticoagulant properties of plant saponin extracts or individual saponins have been reported. From a structural perspective, they are made up of a lipophilic polycyclic aglycone called a sapogenin that is joined to one or more sugar side chains. The structure of saponins and some of their potential benefits in preventing thromboembolic conditions.^[13]

1.6.2. Monounsaturated fatty acids

Monounsaturated fats have the potential to lower blood levels of bad cholesterol, thereby lowering the risk of heart disease and stroke. They also supply nutrients that support the growth and upkeep of body's cells. Oleic acid is the main monounsaturated fat in the diet. Fat molecules with a single unsaturated carbon bond are known as monounsaturated fats. Monounsaturated fat-containing oils are normally liquid at room temperature but begin to solidify when cooled. The overall levels of cholesterol are not significantly affected when MUFAs replace carbohydrates in the diet. In general, total cholesterol levels tend to go down when mono unsaturated fatty acids replace saturated fatty acid in the diet.^[14]

1.7. Molecular docking

Docking is a technique used in molecular modeling that forecasts a molecule's preferred orientation in relation to another when a ligand and a target are bound together to form a stable complex. Because molecular docking can predict how small molecule ligands will bind and conform to the right target binding site, it is one of the most widely used techniques in structure-based drug design. Determining the binding behavior of a drug is crucial for both rational drug design and the understanding of basic biochemical processes. As a result, docking is helpful for anticipating the kind and strength of signal that will be generated.^[15]

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD:

The following steps are required by the in-silico studies. These include the preparation of protein molecules, ligand molecules, prediction of binding sites, molecular docking studies, and docking study evaluation.^[16]

2.1. FABRICATION OF PROTEIN MOLECULES

Utilizing a variety of internet resources is necessary for the synthesis of protein molecules, although the National Centre for Biotechnology Information Protein Information Bank is a particular favorite.

2.2. BY NCBI:

Protein molecules have to fit the requirements needed to look into docking. The server of the National Centre for Biotechnology Information was used to extract the protein molecules. [www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov].^[17]

2.3 BY PDB:

Next, protein molecules like N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) were the focus of docking studies. It is necessary to download the structure from the "Protein Data Bank" [PDB]. Additionally, download the file in PDB format.^[18]

2.4. FABRICATION OF THE LIGAND MOLECULE:

The ligand molecule was retrieved via the Pubchem server [<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>].^[19] An open-source information source for chemistry research is PubChem, provided by the National Institutes of Health (NIH). The ligand molecules "Flabelliferin-A and palmitoleic acid were downloaded in sdf format and using open bubble converted to mol2 format.

2.5. DETERMINATION OF BINDING SITE:

The interaction between a protein and ligand molecule has been critical to a drug's therapeutic activity. The protein-ligand interaction is made possible by the presence of binding molecules in the protein. The ligand molecule was given activity through the protein binding site. Due to the large number of binding sites, the ligand and protein molecules had a high affinity. The binding location needs to be found first.

2.6. BY CASTp:

The CASTp server was utilized to determine the protein molecules' binding locations. A free online tool called the Computed Atlas of Protein Surface Topography (CASTp) can be used to locate, characterize, and measure concave surface areas on three-dimensional protein structures [source:cast.engr.uic.edu]. The goal of CASTp, or the Computer Atlas of Surface Topography of Proteins, is to provide an extensive and comprehensive statistical characterization of the topographic features of proteins.^[20]

2.7. PROTEIN LIGAND DOCKING:

The auto-docking approach is what we have to promote for docking investigations. They required a configuration text document, a vina application file for auto-docking, protein preparation in a pdb file, and ligand preparation in a file in .mol2 format. All four of these are kept in the same folder. To dock, they required the Cygwin and autodock tool applications.

2.8. IN THE AUTO-DOCK TOOL APPLICATION:

The process known as "auto-docking" predicts the optimal location of a single molecule to a later position when ligand and target are joined to form a stable complex. [autodock.scripps.edu (AutoDock)] [autodock vina.scripps.edu (Auto Dock Vina)].^[21]

2.9 IN CYGWIN APPLICATION:

Launch the Cygwin application and enter the location of the folders containing config, vina, protein.pdbqt, and ligand.pdbqt. The program can then be run by typing [./vina -config config.txt &] code. Lastly, the output was supplied as ligand output by Cygwin.

2.10. VISUALISATION OF PROTEIN LIGAND INTERACTION:

The protein pdbqt file and the ligand output file from the Cygwin application were combined for the visualisation, and the resulting mixture was used as the input for the Discovery Studio application. Modeling small and large molecule systems can be done with software called Discovery Studio.^{[22][23]}

III. RESULTS

In addition to investigating Flabelliferin-A and palmitoleic acid targets in stroke treatments, the study assessed the effectiveness of powdered palmyra palm ripe fruit. An optimal stereochemical quality for further research could be provided by evaluating the docking model's stereochemical grade. After the aforementioned assessment, protein-ligand docking studies were conducted to increase confidence. Protein-ligand docking experiments were performed with the confidence that the previously mentioned valuation offered in order to learn more about the most probable and effective Flabelliferin-A and palmitoleic acid interaction conformations with the target protein. The subsections that follow are listed below and contain the results.

3.1 PROTEIN MOLECULE MACHINING:

BY NCBI and BY PDB: The National Center for Biotechnology Information's server was used to retrieve a protein molecule. Then, protein molecules like N-methyl-D-aspartate were chosen for docking investigations. Figure 2 illustrates the structure after it has been retrieved from the "Protein Data Bank" [PDB].

3.2 THE LIGAND MOLECULE'S MACHINING: The Pub chem server was used to get the ligand molecule, which was then converted to (. mol2) format ligand, Flabelliferin-A and Palmitoleic acid displayed in figure 3 and figure 4 respectively.

3.3. DETERMINATION OF BINDING SITE:

The figure 5 show the interaction between proteins and ligand molecules. The protein binding site had been used to provide activity for the ligand molecule. The **CASTp** server found the binding location of the protein molecule.

3.4. PROTEIN LIGAND DOCKING: By using applications like **AUTO-DOCK TOOL** to determine the 3D interaction of protein ligand with Flabelliferin-A and Palmitoleic acid that has shown in figure 6.

The Cygwin report for Flabelliferin A and Palmitoleic acid was given in below table 1.

The binding affinity shows interaction between protein and the ligand. This binding affinity of ligands correlate with their activity. The normal binding affinity for all compound ranges from - 3.2 and -18.5 kcal/mol. Here the binding affinity of Flabelliferin-A is more than Palmitoleic acid.

3.5. VISUALISATION OF PROTEIN LIGAND INTERACTION:

For the visualisation, the intermixing of protein and ligand output had been provided as the input for the Discovery Studio application and the intermixed file shown in figure 7 and figure 8

IV. DISCUSSION:

In this research, we employed bio-informatic techniques to evaluate the efficacy of Flabelliferin-A and Palmitoleic acid against stroke for drug interaction, drug similarity and binding energy calculation. Stroke is one of the cerebrovascular illnesses and the second leading cause of death and disability worldwide. As ischaemic brain damage mediator, N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor plays major role to perform this research to determining the active therapeutic component. For molecular docking, auto-dock Vina was one of these approaches. There was a contrast between Flabelliferin-A and Palmitoleic acid for N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor that investigation found the Flabelliferin-A binding affinity of NMDA receptor has a greater binding site than the palmitoleic acid binding affinity. Both Flabelliferin-A and palmitoleic acid of Palmyra palm had the better activity against the stroke. Among that Flabelliferin-A have proven that have the higher binding affinity than the palmitoleic acid.

Most people agree that H-bonds help proteins bind to ligands. About one order of magnitude is added to binding affinities for each hydrogen bond. The hydrogen bonding length between NMDA and Flabelliferin A is 2.55,2.80,3.08,3.10, the hydrogen bonding length between NMDA and Palmitoleic acid is 2.31,2.71,3.03 respectively. The presence of more hydrogen bond provides more affinity. Simultaneously a greater number of binding sites provides better action. Even every activity of drug that may be positive or negative it depends on binding of ligand to specific site. From the above comparative study, the Flabelliferin A has higher number of hydrogen bonds in relation with Palmitoleic acid.

V. CONCLUSION:

The auto dock software analysed the plant compounds of Flabelliferin-A and Palmitoleic acid. The active substance Flabelliferin A binds to the NMDA-binding site with good affinity than in Palmitoleic acid, according to computational experimental studies revealed that Flabelliferin-A docked compound had a greater binding score ranging from -7.7 to -6.7kcal/mol. which is much better as compared to Palmitoleic acid. In subsequent research, these compounds may serve as a model molecule for the development of plant-based anti-stroke medications.

Figure 1: Pathophysiology of Stroke

Figure 2: N-methyl-D-aspartate

Figure 3: structure of Flabelliferin A

Figure 4: structure of Palmitoleic acid

Figure 5: Binding site of protein molecule

a)

b)

Figure 6: 3D interaction of protein ligand with a) Flabelliferin A and b) Palmitoleic acid

a)

b)

Figure 7: visualisation of 3D structure of protein and ligand interaction with a) Flabelliferin A and b) Palmitoleic acid

a)

b)

Figure 8: Visualisation of 2D structure of protein and ligand interaction with a) Flabelliferin A and b) Palmitoleic acid

Mode	Affinity of NMDA with Flabelliferin A (kcal/mol)	Affinity of NMDA with Palmitoleic acid (kcal/mol)
1	-7.7	-5.7
2	-7.4	-5.4
3	-7.4	-5.4
4	-7.1	-5.4
5	-7.1	-5.3
6	-7.0	-5.3
7	-7.0	-5.3
8	-6.8	-5.3
9	-6.7	-5.2

Table 1: Binding affinity for Flabelliferin A and Palmitoleic acid

Physicochemical properties	Flabelliferin A	Palmitoleic acid
Molecular weight	504.708	254.414
Log p (partition coefficient)	5.6525	5.3283
Rotatable bond	8	13
Hydrogen Acceptor	6	1
Hydrogen Donor	1	1
Surface Area	217.121	112.480

Table 2: Physicochemical parameter of Flabelliferin A and Palmitoleic acid

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Conflict of interest

Nil